

Photo-Luminescence study of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}_{1-x}(\text{BO}_3)_3 : X \text{Ce}^{3+}$ phosphor

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Abstract

The polycrystalline powder sample of Ce^{3+} activated barium gadolinium borate phosphors $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}_{1-x}(\text{BO}_3)_3 : X \text{Ce}^{3+}$ ($0.01 \leq X \leq 0.06$) are prepared by solution combustion. Formation of phosphor in desired crystalline phase confirmed by powder XRD characterization & FTIR. A SEM image shows the irregular grains with average particle size $2.5\mu\text{m}$. The excitation spectrum consists of a single broad absorption band from 200 to 400 nm with the prominent excitation peak at 343 nm [$^2\text{F}_{5/2}$ to $^5\text{D}_1$ of Ce^{3+} ions]. Strongest emission peak of 488nm [$^5\text{D}_1 \rightarrow ^2\text{F}_{5/2}$] and weak of 501nm [$^5\text{D}_1 \rightarrow ^2\text{F}_{7/2}$] wavelength which is of blue light is observed at 343nm UV light excitation. $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}_{1-x}(\text{BO}_3)_3 : X \text{Ce}^{3+}$ phosphor emits blue light under UV excitation. Maximum PL emission takes place at 3 mole percentage of Ce^{3+} . Concentration quenching for Ce^{3+} ions is studied. Hence $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}_{1-x}(\text{BO}_3)_3 : X \text{Ce}^{3+}$ is new UV excited blue emitting phosphor useful for UV/Blue chip WLEDs.

Keywords

Borate phosphor, Photoluminescence, Red emission, W- LED.

1. Introduction

The syntheses of compounds $\text{M}_3\text{Ln}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ M =Sr, Ba and Ln=La–Lu, Sc, Y have been reported in recent past years [1]. The spectroscopic properties of vacuum ultraviolet and x-ray excited Ce^{3+} ion-activated $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ have been reported by Hong-bin Liang et.al. They studied luminescence properties of Ce^{3+} -doped barium gadolinium borate $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3:\text{Ce}^{3+}$ under vuv, uv, and x-ray excitations. $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3:\text{Ce}^{3+}$ is a poor x-ray phosphor. The dopant Ce^{3+} is slightly larger than Gd^{3+} but it will not distort the crystal lattice of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ too seriously and is expected to replace Gd^{3+} ions [2]. $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ doped with Eu^{3+} ion was prepared by high temperature solid-state method and luminescence was studied by ZHOU Liya et.al. $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ phosphor was effectively excited by the near ultraviolet (UV) light (396 nm) and blue light (466 nm). The main

emission peaks are at 611 and 616 nm , it was red emitting phosphor [3]. Cerium trivalent ion has only one 4f electron and only single discrete 4f energy level shielded by the completely filled 5S², 5P⁶orbital. General emission of Ce³⁺ has doublet character with wavelength difference approximately 40nm. Broad emission band is due to inter-configurationally 5d¹-4f¹ allowed transition of Ce³⁺. For blue luminescence Ce³⁺ ions is worthy to use in phosphors. For the important point of application, each proper mono-color-blue LED phosphor must meet the following necessary conditions. (1) The phosphor must show higher thermal stability. (2) The phosphor must efficiently absorb the 340nm - 400nm excitation energy. (3) The CIE coordinates of the phosphor are close to the NTSC standard values. BaMgAl₁₀O₁₇:Eu²⁺ (BAM) is one kind of reported commercial blue phosphor used in fluorescent lamps, because of its efficient blue emission [11]. Ca₂B₅O₉Cl:Eu²⁺, is another suitable Blue-Emitting Phosphor for n-UV Excited Solid-State Lighting [12]. Ca₂Pb₃(PO₄)₃Cl : Ce³⁺ is recently reported blue emitting lamp phosphor [13]. Sr_{1-x}Ca_xLu₂O₄:Ce³⁺ is blue phosphor for high CRI white LEDs [14-15].

2. Experimental

Phosphors were prepared by the solution combustion synthesis [4,5]. Stoichiometric amounts of high purity starting materials, Ba(NO₃)₂ (A.R.), H₃BO₃ (A.R.), CO(NH₂)₂ (A.R.), Gd(NO₃)₃.6H₂O (A.R.), Ce(NO₃)₃.6H₂O as given in table (1) are used for phosphor preparation. All chemicals from Merck of AR grade of (99.99%) purity. The starting materials with little amount of double distilled water were mixed thoroughly in agate mortar to obtain a homogeneous solution. Excess water was removed by heating the samples at temperature 100°C for about 30 min and the paste was then transferred directly to a pre-heated Muffle furnace, maintained at temperature 680°C, for combustion. Following the combustion, the resulting foamy samples was crushed to obtain fine particles and then annealed for 3 h at temperature 950°C. As prepared Borate phosphor material was characterized by powder XRD, SEM, PL and FT-IR techniques. Surface morphology and elemental analysis of the calcined powder sample was observed by scanning electron microscopy [SEM:Model JSM6100 (Jeol)].

Table 1 Merck -AR grade chemicals used for synthesis

Ba₃Gd_{0.97}(BO₃)₃ : 0.03 Ce³⁺					
Precursors	Ba(NO₃)₂	Gd(NO₃)₂	H₃BO₃	NH₂CONH₂	Ce(NO₃)₃.6H₂O
Molar ratio	3	0.96	3	7.45	0.04
Weight in gm	7.8405	1.08388	1.853	4.4744	0.194028

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. X-ray diffraction

Powder X-ray diffraction measurements of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}_{0.970}0.03\text{Ce}^{3+}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ phosphor were taken on a Rigaku Miniflex II X-ray Diffractometer and compared with JCPDS No.(52-1327) as shown in figure 1-A. The maximum peaks matches with the standard pattern. The additional peaks are present in recorded pattern are due to impurities. Sharp peaks in XRD pattern are due to large crystallite size. X-ray pattern of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ matches with the X-ray pattern of low temperature phase of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Y}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ [1,2]. Space group of phosphor $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ is $R\bar{3}(148)$ and cell parameters are $a = 13.06$, $c = 9.552$. $V = 1412.42 \text{ \AA}^3$. A detailed structure description of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ was not found in literature. Bing Han *et al.* in his work mentioned that $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ is isomorphic with $H\text{-Ba}_3\text{Y}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ for the following three reasons: (i) The powder XRD patterns of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ and $H\text{-Ba}_3\text{Y}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ are similar. (ii) The ionic radii of Gd^{3+} [$R_{\text{Gd(III)}}$] = 93.8 pm are close to that of Y^{3+} [$R_{\text{Y(III)}}$] = 90.0 pm in six fold coordination. (iii) It was found that the unit cell parameters [$a = 13.067(3) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9.552(3) \text{ \AA}$, trigonal, $R\bar{3}$] of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ are similar with that [$a = 13.028(2) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9.4992(2) \text{ \AA}$, trigonal, $R\bar{3}$] of $H\text{-Ba}_3\text{Y}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ [2]. In a high temperature phase, a $H\text{-Ba}_3\text{Y}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ with a trigonal system having a space group of $R(3)$, $Z = 6$, which consists of YB_6O_{18} unit with polyhedral of BaO_6 and BaO_8 as shown in figure 1-B [16].

Figure 1-A:XRD-pattern of sample1-B:Structural unit of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Y}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ with six fold coordination of Y^{3+} ions [17]

3.2. SEM

SEM study was carried out to examine the surface morphology of the prepared phosphor. The SEM images of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}_{1-0.03}(\text{BO}_3)_3:0.03\text{Ce}^{3+}$ phosphors are shown in Figure 2. It was

observed that the microstructure of the phosphor consist of irregular grains with agglomerate phenomena. The average size of synthesized phosphor particles is about 50 μm . The results show that phosphors have a good crystallinity and a relatively low sinter temperature. Average crystalline size by Scherrer formula is in 42.2 nm, which is nearly same as seen in surface morphology. SEM shows the image of polycrystalline particles and XRD measurements reflect the crystalline domain size. It indicates that solution combustion synthesized phosphor has sharp surface morphology as well as crystalline grains.

Figure 2: SEM Image of phosphor host.

3.3. PL and PLE Study

The PLE of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Gd}_{0.97}(\text{BO}_3)_3 : 0.03\text{Ce}^{3+}$ phosphor is shown in figure (3). It is recorded on F-7000 FL spectrophotometer with scan speed 240 nm/min, excitation-emission slit width 1nm. Ce^{3+} is all-round candidate for phosphor materials and it does not have any 4f-4f transition. It shows only 4f-5d type inter configurationally transition in borate host [8,9,10]. Photoluminescence excitation is broad band in region 240nm to 400nm with shoulder peak at 343nm due to transition from $^2\text{F}_{5/2}$ to $^5\text{d}_1$ level of activator ion in host lattice.

Figure 3 PLE of $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03 Ce^{3+}$ **Figure 4** PL of $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03 Ce^{3+}$

The PL of $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03 Ce^{3+}$ phosphor monitored at 343nm excitation is shown in figure (4). PL recorded in range 450nm to 530nm shows two peaks at 488nm and 501nm. 488nm peak is due to 5d_1 to $^2F_{5/2}$ and 501nm peak is due to 5d_1 to $^2F_{7/2}$ transition of activator in crystal environment. Ce^{3+} ion shown the two characteristic lines. Intensity of 501nm is less than 488nm line. 488nm lies in blue region of spectrum. So it is NUV excited blue emitting phosphor. The photoluminescence study is carried out at room temperature.

Figure 5 PL of host phosphor at different concentration of dopant Ce^{3+} And embedded Concentration quenching Curve

3.4. CIE Chromaticity Diagram of $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03 Ce^{3+}$

Figure (6) shows the Commission International del Eclairage (CIE) chromaticity coordinates diagram of the $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03 Ce^{3+}$ phosphor at 488nm. The chromaticity coordinates of the phosphor $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03Ce^{3+}$ for fixed concentration of Ce^{3+} at 488 nm was computed using LEDTUNING. NL Software [<https://www.ledtuning.nl/en/cie-convertoor>][11-12-13]. CIE Chromaticity co-ordinates for $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03Ce^{3+}$ at PL wavelength 488nm are $X = 0.05467$, $Y = 0.2541$. It comes in blue region of CIE Chromaticity diagram and is indicated by black circle in figure(6). CCT value is 122321 kelvin and Delta uv is 0.1402.

Figure 6 CIE chromaticity of $Ba_3Gd_{0.97}(BO_3)_3 : 0.03 Ce^{3+}$

4. Conclusions

The $Ba_3Gd_{1-x}(BO_3)_3 : X Ce^{3+}$ polycrystalline phosphor was synthesized by solution combustion method. XRD confirmed the phase & formation of compound and it matches with standard JCPDS file number 52-1327. SEM shows the average size of synthesized phosphor particles was about 2.5 μm and good crystalline. Phosphor shows broad excitation band from 200 to 400 nm with prominent peak at 343 nm. PLE for characteristic emission wavelength 488 nm was found to be 343 nm. At 343 nm, UV light excitation $Ba_3Gd_{1-x}(BO_3)_3 : X Ce^{3+}$ phosphor emits blue light.

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